

Original article

ROLE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS IN ATTRACTING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS: CASE STUDY ON ROMANIA

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Abstract: Foreign direct investment plays a critical role in Romania's economic development and integration into EU value chains. However, attracting FDI at the county level remains a challenge due to infrastructure gaps, regulatory instability, and inconsistent investment support. This study examines how Romanian local governments facilitate FDI, identifying key incentives, barriers, and strategic alignment with EU priorities such as the Green Transition and Digitalization. Using a descriptive-qualitative approach, the research involved responses from 17 local administrations, highlighting regional disparities in FDI attraction strategies. Findings suggest that counties struggle with bureaucratic inefficiencies, labor shortages, and inadequate transport infrastructure, deterring potential investors. While local governments seek to enhance investment conditions through fiscal incentives, improved public services, and industrial park development, their efforts are often hindered by limited coordination with central authorities. The study underscores the need for a comprehensive "Made in Romania" strategy, stronger public-private collaboration, and targeted public investments to enhance competitiveness. It calls for further multi-stakeholder research to assess local FDI policies, streamline administrative processes, and align regional development strategies with EU industrial and economic policies. These findings provide insights for policymakers aiming to strengthen Romania's position within the European investment landscape.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment, Local Administration, Investment Incentives, EU Value Chains, Economic Development

JEL classification: G10, H83, R50, F63

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1. Introduction

The EU's strategic value chain represents an integrated and coordinated approach to the EU's industrial, economic, and innovation policies aimed at supporting strategic sectors, enhancing competitiveness, ensuring sustainability, and driving innovation (table 1).

Table 1: Dimensions of the EU strategic value chain

Dimensions of the EU strategic value chain	Directions
1. Technological Innovation	The value chain relies on leveraging key technologies, technological progress, research and development outcomes, or disruptive innovations (e.g., autonomous driving, low CO2 emission technologies).
2. Economic and Market Potential	The value chain holds considerable significance in terms of economic impact and market presence.
3. Societal and Political Importance	The value chain addresses societal challenges and/or European policy goals (e.g., climate change, population aging). It is also crucial for Europe's security and autonomy.

Source: the author (2024)

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The automotive sector will be one of the major end-user segments for lithium-ion batteries soon. A range of different vehicle types are now available globally, offering increasing degrees of hybridization and electrification: hybrid electric vehicles, plug-in hybrid electric vehicles and electric vehicles. The penetration of electric vehicles is anticipated to provide a massive boost to the lithium-ion battery industry (Gusilov and Staicu, 2023). For example, the European battery value chain is part of chain 1 (table 1), and the Commission has identified batteries as a strategic value chain where the EU needs to increase investment, as they are essential for decarbonizing mobility, the transition to a climate-neutral economy and many other areas. The EC promotes a cross-border and integrated European approach covering the entire value chain of the battery ecosystem, from extraction and processing of raw materials, design and manufacture of battery cells and battery packs and use; second use, recycling and disposal.

International capital flows are increasingly shaping the global economy. There is a growing significance of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) among investors (PwC, 2013). However, in 2012, the region's average GDP per capita, adjusted for purchasing power parity, was only 57% of the Western European average. As a result, CEE countries must provide even better conditions for both domestic and foreign investors. According to Orłowski (PwC, 2013), lower labor costs are no longer sufficient, and strategies are needed to enhance competitive advantage over other regions in attracting foreign direct investments (FDI).

The growing competition for FDI is likely to drive authorities at various levels to implement policies aimed at influencing FDI patterns (Rao et al., 2020). Establishing institutions to support economic and social development in Central and Eastern Europe, fostering entrepreneurship through new technologies to diversify and improve production, assisting in research and market exploration, and creating favorable conditions and consistent programs to attract and support foreign investors—these are actions that local and regional authorities can take to stimulate growth.

In the process of policy implementation for integration in the EU value chains, the critical role of local governments in designing development programs for their regions and attracting FDI's cannot be overlooked. Local governments can undertake four key tasks that shape the investment climate in their area: develop and maintain infrastructure to facilitate the initiation, operation, and growth of economic activities; promote the region and provide thorough information to potential investors; deliver efficient and professional administrative services; create favorable financial conditions for starting and expanding businesses, such as through State aid schemes (Nurani et al., 2019; Dorożyński et al., 2014).

Foreign investors are particularly drawn to markets with positive indicators such as large market size, high population, and economic stability. Additionally, the governance situation of a country can be a dynamic factor that significantly influences the inflow of FDI (Tabash, 2024). Therefore, improved governance can attract more investors, as effective governance signals political stability, reduced information asymmetry, effective corruption control (Raza et al., 2021). Studies on the involvement of local authorities or governments in supporting foreign direct investment (FDI) are relatively rare (PwC, 2013).

This research is organized as follows. First, we discuss findings from literature. Second, we describe the tools available to attract investors at the local level. Third, we describe the empirical analysis based on qualitative data collected directly from seventeen local administrations in Romania. Finally, conclusions are drawn, and recommendations are formulated.

2. Problem statement

According to Gusilov and Staicu (2023), recommendations for Romania to become part of the EU value chains, include the articulation of a "Made in Romania" strategy, public investments to help less competitive regions improve their performance and close the gap, while also ensuring that the most competitive regions continue to thrive. Romania has considerable potential, which must be mapped, monitored, and developed with the help of NATO and EU allies. The approaches may vary from development through specialized clusters to public-private partnerships (PPPs). What is important is that this activity is closely aligned with the EU's industrial policy and sectoral strategies (in solar, wind, hydrogen, storage, etc.), so it does not run counter to Europe's energy and environmental policy but works in tandem with it.

Responsibilities for attracting and supporting foreign investors in Romania are shared between central and local governments. The central administration, including key ministries like Economy, Finance, and European Investments, along with the Romanian Agency for Investments and Foreign Trade, coordinates national FDI policy. They manage budgetary resources and EU funds, including those from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan. At this point, it is not clear how Romanian local authorities from each county attract FDI to align to EU economic priorities. No research in this area has been published yet.

3. Research question

There are numerous tools available to attract investors: investment incentives are particularly important, as they can influence the size, location, or sector of the planned investment (World Trade Report, 2006). Second, financial incentives such as primarily subsidies and tax allowances are undoubtedly the most significant. Moreover, surveys indicate that investors also value preferential access to public services and subsidies for starting and expanding businesses. Additionally, foreign investors appreciate support related to information and promotion, such as free information and business advisory services (Harding and Javorcik, 2011).

This chapter aims to evaluate local government’s efforts undertaken to attract FDI by understanding how local administrations in Romania view the subject. In this direction, the research inquired about: the facilities granted by the local administration to investors; priority areas for investment from the perspective of local administrations; difficulties in negotiations between local administrations and investors; support of central government in attracting investors.

4. Research methods

This research employed a descriptive-qualitative approach.

Data collection was carried out through administering a questionnaire to 41 local administrations in Romania (table 2) excluding Bucharest.

The Bucharest-Ilfov development region is not represented in the study because current economic data show stable and continuous development in this region, responsible for 25% of the national economy and with a GDP per capita of 49,200 euros, about 164% of the European average (Eurostat 2022, data from 2020). However, this region has been the subject of previous research (Dorożyński et al., 2014).

4.1. Sample information

The sample was considered relevant when all Romania’s regions (table 2) were represented by at least one respondent. Seventeen local administrations from all regions responded to the questionnaire, with most counties represented in the study being from the South-East development region which was represented by five local administrations that responded to the request. A detailed structure of the sample is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Questionnaire respondents by development region

Romania’s development regions	Counties’ respondents
North – East	Botoșani, Suceava și Vaslui (3)
South - East	Brăila, Buzău, Constanța, Vrancea și Tulcea (5)
South - Muntenia	Călărași, Giurgiu, Ialomița (3)
South - West Oltenia	Gorj, Olt și Vâlcea (3)
West	Arad (1)
North - West	Sălaj, Satu–Mare (2)
Center	Harghita (1)

Source: the author (2023)

Arad county (West region) and Botosani county (North-East) offered the most descriptive answers to the questionnaire and offered the possibility to the author to map the county’s resources in-depth in section 5 of this research.

4.2 Questionnaire

The questionnaire was designed to comprise only five questions to get more respondents to agree to it and it is meant to open a pathway for in-depth research related to the role of local government in attracting foreign direct investments (table 3). All questions were open-ended as one of the goals of the study was to explore the local government opinions towards FDI incentives and barriers.

Table 3: Questionnaire administered to the local administrations in Romania

1. What are the facilities provided by the local administration that attract FDI in your county?
2. In which areas did you intend to attract investors to open a business (production or services) in your county?
3. Why did you choose the respective fields?
4. What are the difficulties you encounter in negotiations with investors?
5. How can the central administration support you in attracting investors?

Source: the author (2023)

During the questioning stage of the relevant actors, the researcher engaged in an extensive dialogue with the reps of local administrations. The level of discussions and access to in-depth information varied with each representative interviewed. Therefore, research also includes an original component of sensitization and awareness for key actors from the public and private sectors in Romania.

4.3 Data anonymity and consent

In this data collection, the principles of anonymity and consent were followed. In regards with data storage, the data collected was stored in the researcher’s computer and erased from the online platform employed for data collection. The access to the computer is limited only to the researcher and protected by password. In terms of data processing, pseudonymization was employed: the identifying information for each local council respondent was changed for codes employed during analysis to further protect respondent identities. For reasons of GDPR, the name of the respondent was not required, only the name of the institution the person represented in the case of this questionnaire. The communication with Respondents was clear: Before starting the interview, the researcher communicated how the data collected will be used, stored, and protected. The respondents were informed that they have the right to withdraw their data from the study at any time. By following these practices, the researcher ensured that the confidentiality of respondents to the interview is maintained, protecting their privacy and upholding the integrity of the research.

5. Findings

5.1 The facilities granted by the local administration that attract investors to invest in an area or region vary from infrastructure development solutions to the mapping of material and immaterial resources in the county (table 4).

Table 4: Facilities granted by the local administration to attract investors

Development of county infrastructure	Fiscal policy	Access to qualified human resources	Access to land for business development	Mapping the resources of the county
modernized road infrastructure	tax reductions/exemptions (e.g. on land/ buildings the investor will use for its activity)	specialized workforce training (creation of a university campus, stimulation of dual education, curriculum harmonized with the labor market)	shortening the period for obtaining construction permits, free issuance of any town planning certificates and building permits	information about the surface for fish farming development
access to railway infrastructure, energy (e.g. power supply for industrial platforms)	adoption/reconfiguration of minimis schemes to stimulate investment	facilitating access to human resources in the border area: access to the labor force in the vicinity	grant of land for exploitation	models for development for agritourism (e.g. cultural tourism, landscape tourism); mapping of traditions, customs, natural/architectural monuments
access to airport infrastructure	information on state aid schemes	making available real estate, land and buildings, with	mobile phone services coverage	investment models in the field of textiles

(e.g. cargo terminal)		rental or concession options		
access to land with installed utilities	community programs to support investments in environmental protection, rehabilitation and expansion of communication routes, power supply, sewage and purification systems and waste management		access to industrial parks (e.g. Suceava: "Bucovina Industrial Park", "East European Border Siret Industrial Park")	mapping underground mineral resources and construction materials for development of integrated exploitations
public transportation to industrial areas				

Source: the author (2023)

In research focused on Poland (PwC, 2013) and the role of local government units in attracting FDI, the most frequently highlighted advantage is the positive impact of foreign investment on job creation, where respondents noted that their local governments are eager to welcome any investor who generates new employment opportunities, provided they comply with environmental regulations.

5.2 When asked the question "In which areas did you intend to attract investors to open a business (production or services) in your county?", local administrations specified 10 areas (figure 2). About two-thirds of respondents have sectoral preferences (figure 1).

Others focus primarily on projects in sectors where a commune or county offers favourable conditions, such as: labour resources with specialized skills; natural conditions conducive to tourism in landscape parks, wind energy, or geothermal water use; intensive agricultural production supporting various agricultural and food processing activities; locations along transportation routes or public transit that are ideal for expanding logistics parks.

Figure 1: Priority areas for attracting investors

Source: the author (2023)

The most frequently mentioned areas in which local authorities want to attract investments are tourism, renewable energy, agriculture, production, without specifying what exactly they want to produce.

Three of the 17 county authorities mentioned that they want to attract investors "in all fields", which shows that those authorities do not have a strategy by which to correlate local material resources and human resources with certain development sectors in which to make investments that would attract the interest of investors (e.g. if the focus is on renewable energy production you need land for the installation of solar panels, panel supplier, specialists in managing this type of project, access to the grid, understanding the ecosystem that is necessary for the operation of such of local businesses and to facilitate access to authorizations, etc.). In another county, the strategy for local development and attracting investors is closely linked to open financing lines: "Depending on the open funding lines

and the existing needs at the county level, funding applications are drawn up in order to obtain non-refundable funding in the following areas of investment: heritage (infrastructure, endowments), public health (infrastructure, endowments, digitization, training courses training), education (educational infrastructure, facilities), transport (road infrastructure), tourism (tourist infrastructure), environment, energy efficiency, administrative capacity, etc."

In another county, the local development and investor attraction strategy is closely tied to the available funding lines: "Based on the available funding lines and the existing needs at the county level, funding applications are prepared to obtain non-reimbursable financing in the following investment areas: heritage (infrastructure, equipment), public health (infrastructure, equipment, digitalization, training courses), education (educational infrastructure, equipment), transportation (road infrastructure), tourism (tourist infrastructure), environment, energy efficiency, administrative capacity, etc."

In fact, all the counties are interested in investments creating new jobs in their areas. Some indicated the need to attract environmentally friendly projects. Pressure on other kinds of investments is focused on domains which align to the county's Strategy for Sustainable Development. This strategy is a strategic roadmap document developed by each county council, which outlines the main directions for economic, social, and infrastructure development of a county in the medium and long term. The current strategy (2021 – 2027) includes development objectives, investment priorities, action plans, and the resources needed to achieve these objectives, and aims to improve the quality of life for residents, stimulate economic growth, and ensure a sustainable social and economic environment.

Compared to EU priorities outlined in Chapter 1, we notice a gap in aligning priorities between EU and Romanian authorities (figure 2) none of the respondents mentioning projects related to smart health, internet of things for industry or cyber security.

Figure 2: The gap between EU priority directions and local authorities in Romania

Source: the author based on Strategic Forum for IPCEI (2019) and the questionnaire (2023).

A particular mapping of county resources was carried out throughout the interview by the local council of Botoșani, and its representative highlighted the resources in the county that can be exploited by investors (figure 3). This mapping is clear and indicates that this is not a first exercise of this type done by this administration.

Figure 3: Map of local resources (Botoșani county) to attract local investors

Source: the author (2023)

5.3 When asked, "Why did you choose those specific areas for FDI?", the motivations of the local administrations varied. One response explains the connection between the priority areas for attracting investments and the material resources in a county. In the case of the agriculture sector, these resources include fertile soil, the diversity of plant varieties that can be cultivated, the vast area of agricultural land (farmland, arable land, pastures, meadows, orchards), the existence of naval transport infrastructure (e.g., proximity to the Danube), and a young workforce to engage in vegetable farming.

The automotive, metallurgical industry, and energy production sectors are preferred in a particular county because of the already existing infrastructure (the authorities focus more on what is currently available rather than on what can be created with future technologies): "There is a well-developed industrial platform with companies in these fields and with potential for growth."

The production and use of hydrogen, a EU priority as well, was selected as a priority activity by one of the counties for attracting investments because they are looking toward the future. *"In the context of the surge in the number of investment projects in alternative energy production and considering that the national energy system does not have the capacity to capture all the energy produced, investments in storage facilities are needed. An alternative to storage batteries, which are extremely expensive and have limited capacity, is the production of hydrogen through electrolysis."*

One case was chosen to reflect the motivations of the local administration for its choice of priority areas for investment, because the motivations list was complex (figure 4).

Figure 4: Arad county: the motifs for the selection of priority areas for investment

Source: the author (2023)

Three county authorities mention that they follow a roadmap developed for 2021 – 2017 entitled “The sustainable development strategy”, mandatory document for each county administration. Many answers given related to the reasons why certain activities are prioritized for attracting investments, are general with reference to "relief, climate, traditions and customs or because those activities have the greatest potential for development and are tailored to the specifics of the county", answers denoting that there are no arguments for the prioritization of the areas for attracting investments resulting from a rigorous process of identification and planning of building support ecosystems for the priority areas according to the EU development directions, sources of European funding (which are already open or are following), technologies related to digitization and greening of industry (from electric vehicles to hydrogen production, renewable energy, green energy, industry decarbonization solutions).

5.4 The respondents identified ten categories of difficulties in the public-private partnership when asked the question "What are the difficulties you encounter in negotiations with investors?" (figure 5).

Figure 5: Difficulties in the relationship between local administration and investors

Source: the author (2023)

Respondents emphasized most strongly that the regulations and procedures were overly complex, time-consuming, unclear, and lacked transparency. The most critical comments were directed at procedures related to construction, including those involving land acquisition and construction law. The legislation was characterized by

the respondents as “unpredictable, rigid, volatile, thick, restrictive”, and was mentioned by two-thirds of the respondents as main reason creating difficulties in attracting FDI’s. When it comes to tax cuts, Arad County representative specified that access to tax facilities is difficult because it is centralized and there are better tax facilities in other European countries. One of the respondents mentioned that “*They want fiscal facilities, which, however, are not within the reach of local administrations, but depend on ministries or the Government. A difficulty is the fact that in other European countries they receive these facilities, but not in Romania. Because of this, Arad County lost very large investments, worth billions of euros, just in the last year. For one of them we proposed a 700-ha plot, for the other a 1,000 ha plot. Both would have created between 3,000 – 5,000 jobs and would have involved the opening of new school, pre-university and university specializations.*”

The most frequently invoked argument related to the difficulties in negotiations with investors was related to the labour force characterized by “*lack of qualified personnel, small number of the young population able to work*”. According to half of the respondents, there is a significant shortage of workers with the necessary skills in the region. One third of the respondents also mentioned difficulties related to poor transport infrastructure, road and railway, which leads to lack of confidence of investors in the administration. The evaluation of roads highlighted significant criticism regarding the lack of motorways and highways, as well as the slow progress in their construction. It should be noted that three of the 17 respondents mentioned that they had no difficulties in negotiating with investors, and this result likely reflects the respondents' lack of awareness about the investments and needs of entrepreneurs.

In research by Dorożyński et al. (2014), other infrastructure-related challenges include issues with power generation, gas availability, investment areas, water supply, sewage systems, and water treatment plants, which are considered less critical. Complaints have been raised about insufficient electricity transfer capacity, poor-quality distribution lines, and inadequate coordination between gas and energy suppliers and local governments. Sewage and water management in many rural communes faced criticism. It was suggested that the shortage of investment plots and the need to acquire land from multiple owners might deter potential investors. These difficulties, however, have not been mentioned by these respondents.

5.5 Two-thirds of the respondents mentioned attractive taxation, stable legislation and access to financing needed in attracting investors (table 5).

Table 5: Central administration instruments to support local administration in attracting FDI

Financing	Financing lines dedicated to certain types of investments
	Financial aid for major investments in mountain and rural areas
	For setting up industrial parks/innovation research hubs
Legislation and procedures	Simplifying procedures for access to financial resources
	Legislative simplification for approval of works
	Stable legislative climate
	Corroboration of the duties of a UAT with the legislation in PPP
Fiscality	More attractive fees and taxes compared to other states in the region
Education	Encouraging vocational and technical education with a coherent package of measures.
	Developing and supporting vocational and/or dual education.
Infrastructure	Development of the highway network on the major transport routes in Romania
Networking	Establishing collaborative relationships with potential investors at the national level
	Creation of an online database for investors to bids submitted by local investors

Source: the author (2023)

The most frequently mentioned instruments for supporting local administrations were access to financial resources and to fiscal facilities. The most novel mention of support from the national level to the local level came “*in expertise in making investments and networking*”. It was mentioned the need for an Investor Assistance Center in each region corroborated with an online database to connect investors with local governments and other local businesses.

When it comes to financing lines dedicated to certain types of investments, a few examples were provided in particular: investments in the modernization of road infrastructure, tourism, renewable energy, agriculture, industrial parks. One of the respondents specified that one of the instruments through which the central administration can support the local administration is by granting tax facilities for large investors. For example, he mentions a negative situation encountered: “*We lost an investment estimated at over 1 billion euros, from a car battery manufacturer in China, which asked for relief. The Romanian state did not grant them, instead it received them from the Hungarian state, which last month announced the completion of the investment. Or we lost an investment in the*

manufacture of passenger cars, because the Turkish state offered the facilities requested by the investor, and the Romanian state did not. We believe that it would be necessary at the government level to have flexibility regarding the negotiation of strategic investments, because local authorities do not have powers in this regard, and we cannot make promises of a fiscal nature or even the development of large infrastructure. The car manufacturer asked us to supplement the Nădlac customs with a lane and increase the capacity of the electricity network in the west of the country, from Bucharest it is difficult to get a commitment.”

One third of the respondents emphasized a need for encouraging vocational and technical education with a coherent set of measures.

Only one respondent specified that it is necessary to stimulate research and development activities as a solution for development.

When looking at the answers provided for questions 4 and 5 (table 1), we notice a gap between the areas creating difficulty with the investors and the instruments the local government ask from the central authorities (figure 6).

Figure 6: Gap between investor needs and local government requests to central authorities

Source: the author, based on the questionnaire data (2023)

6. Conclusions and recommendations

Given the limited availability of internal capital, foreign investment plays a crucial role in regional development, with its impact being most evident in the labour market. Local governments can influence the economy both directly and indirectly by providing infrastructure, promoting the region, developing investment areas, and implementing EU projects. Their effective operations are essential for the success of businesses in the region, including those involving foreign direct investment.

This research indicates that Romania’s local governments’ efforts to support investors have significant room for improvement. Foreign investors are mainly deterred by issues related to procedures, laws, infrastructure, the business environment, human resources skills, and the labour market. Some of these areas fall under local government responsibilities, some such as legislation under the central government responsibility. The most discouraging factors are related to transport infrastructure and regulatory constraints, especially their instability.

The Romanian state remains the country’s largest and most generous employer. With over 1.3 million employees, Romania ranks fourth in the European Union in terms of budgetary spending on public sector salaries relative to the total budget (capital.ro, 2024). In many Romanian counties (such as Vaslui, Salaj, Teleorman), local governments are now among the largest local investors, employers, and owners of capital.

With access to EU resources and expanding responsibilities, local governments are expected to do more than just promote and administer entrepreneurship. They must operate as business-like entities in local and regional economic matters, manage resources efficiently, professionally oversee their operations and staff, and shape

economic policy by creating favourable conditions for business activity and development. Consequently, the most important change needed is in the management of local and regional public administration, which should facilitate the gradual removal of development obstacles.

Certainly, the study does not cover all aspects of how regional and local public administration attracts and retains foreign investors. Further and more in-depth and multi-stakeholder research is mandatory, particularly involving FDI entities that can evaluate the effectiveness and activities of local authorities as well. A higher number of public administrations should be interested in engaging in this type of research as the results could support their efforts in the dialogue with the central administration.

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